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האוניברסיטה העברית בירושלים
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Molecular gas during the winding-down of star formation

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A star formation peak around $z \simeq 2-3$

Our Galaxy only forms a few stars per year, as most nearby spiral galaxies. Ten billion years ago, between redshift $z=1-3$, the star formation rate (SFR) could be up to 10-20 times higher.

Madau & Dickinson (2014)

- Is the evolution of the cosmic SFR after the star formation peak mostly driven by the available cold gas reservoir, or were the star formation processes qualitatively different?

The Main Sequence of star-forming galaxies

Blue star-forming galaxies lie on a tight relationship in the $M_{\text{star}}/\text{SFR}$ plane, the Main Sequence (MS).

- ▶ Sersic index: $n = 1$ exponential disks vs. $n=4$ de Vaucouleurs profiles (ellipticals)
- ▶ About 90% of the cosmic star formation history since $z \lesssim 2.5$ took place near the MS (Rodighiero et al. 2011, Sargent et al. 2012)

The IRAM PHIBSS survey

IRAM Plateau de Bure High-z Blue Sequence CO(3-2) Survey
(PIs: Linda Tacconi & Françoise Combes)

- a statistical sample of galaxies at high redshift to better understand the winding down of star formation
- traces the cold molecular gas from which stars form with CO rotational lines
- includes high-resolution imaging to study the star formation efficiency at sub-galactic scales

- ▶ two redshift slices: $z=1.2$ and 2.2
- ▶ massive tail of the star forming Main Sequence
($\log(M_{\text{star}}/M_{\odot}) \geq 10.4$, $\text{SFR} \geq 32 M_{\odot}\text{yr}^{-1}$)
- ▶ 52 CO detections (FWHM $\sim 2\text{-}4''$), 8 high-resolution imaging (FWHM $\sim 0.3\text{-}1''$)

PHIBSS highlights: Gas-rich, rotating, turbulent disks

- ▶ Large molecular gas fractions at high redshift: 30-50% at $z \sim 1 - 2$ ($\sim 8\%$ at $z=0$, Saintonge et al. 2011)
- ▶ Sub-arcsecond galaxy kinematics give access to good quality rotation curves and to the velocity dispersion
- ▶ Rotationally-supported turbulent disks, with $v_{\text{rot}}/\sigma \sim 5 - 7$ (Tacconi et al. 2013) ($v_{\text{rot}}/\sigma \sim 10 - 20$ at low-redshift, Dib et al. 2006)

Tacconi et al. (2010)

PHIBSS highlights: the KS relation at high redshift

- ▶ Near-linear molecular KS relation at $z = 1 - 3$, with a median depletion time of 0.7 Gyr
- ▶ Small variation of the depletion time with redshift ($t_{\text{depl}} \sim 2$ Gyr at $z=0$).

Tacconi et al. (2013)

PHIBSS highlights: Resolved KS relations at high redshift

- ▶ Freundlich et al. (2013) : a resolved KS relation for ensembles of clumps separated through their ordered kinematics within four galaxies at $z = 1.2$
- ▶ Genzel et al. (2013): a pixel by pixel KS relation, taking into account extinction (HST multiband maps) and $H\alpha$ observations (LUCI LBT) for one typical massive star-forming galaxy at $z = 1.53$.

The PHIBSS2 Legacy Program (2013-2017)

PIs: F. Combes, S. Garcia-Burillo, R. Neri, & L. Tacconi
Data reduction at IRAM: J. Boissier, C. Feruglio, & R. Neri
Phased with the NOEMA upgrade of the PdB interferometer

- Investigate the interplay between SFR and molecular gas reservoirs
- Cover the **build-up** ($z \sim 2.5 - 3$), the **peak** ($z = 1 - 2$) and the **winding-down** ($z < 1$) of massive galaxy formation
- Better sampling of the $M_{\text{star}}/\text{SFR}$ plane, including galaxies **on and below the MS**, more than **120 targets**
- Characterize the dependence of molecular depletion time and gas fraction with redshift, stellar mass and offset from the MS
- Test the impact of AGNs, environment and morphology owing to a purely mass-selected sample
- High-resolution follow-ups: spatially- resolved KS, rotation curves, velocity dispersion

Upcoming NOEMA interferometer at the Plateau de Bure

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T. Naab (MPA – Germany)

A. Omont (IAP – France)

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A. Saintonge (MPE – Germany)

P. Salomé (Obs. Paris – France)

A. Sternberg (Univ. Tel Aviv – Israel)

F. Walter (MPIA – Germany)

B. Weiner (Steward Obs. Arizona – US)

A. Weiß (MPIR – Germany)

S. Wuyts (MPE – Germany)

The PHIBSS2 samples

- ▶ Probe the molecular gas in the range $z = 0.5 - 0.8$
- ▶ Below the main sequence at $z = 1 - 1.6$
- ▶ Double the statistics at $z = 2 - 2.5$

Sample selection:

- ▶ Well-understood parent samples (GOODS-N, COSMOS, AEGIS)
- ▶ Homogeneous coverage of the MS and its scatter in the M_{star} -SFR plane, with $\log(M_{\text{star}}/M_{\odot}) \geq 10.1$ and $\text{SFR} \geq 3.5 M_{\odot} \text{yr}^{-1}$
- ▶ No morphological selection

Scaling relations

Genzel et al. 2015, Tacconi et al. 2017:

- ▶ 640 CO molecular gas measurements, 751 dust measurements, total 1411
- ▶ 217 z=0 galaxies from COLDGASS, 52 from PHIBSS, 78 from PHIBSS2
- ▶ Dependence of the depletion time and the gas fraction as a function of z, M_{star} and the offset from the MS, $\Delta_{\text{MS}} = \log(\text{SSFR}/\text{SSFR}_{\text{MS}})$

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- - - $\log(M_{\text{molgas}}/M_*) = -1.19x^2 + 3.24x - 1.29$
- - - $\log(M_{\text{molgas}}/M_*) = -1.35 + 2.97x$
- dust 11 μm photometry
- ▲ dust SED Santini+14
- ▼ dust SED Bethermin+15
- dust SED Magnelli+14, Bert+16
- CO

$$- - \log(M_{\text{molgas}}/M_*)_{\text{ms}, \log M_* = 10.7} = +0.53 \log \delta_{\text{ms}}$$

Scaling relations

Genzel et al. 2015, Tacconi et al. 2017:

- ▶ $t_{\text{depl}} \propto (1+z)^{-0.57} \left(\frac{\text{SSFR}}{\text{SSFR}_{\text{MS}}} \right)^{-0.44} \left(\frac{M_{\text{star}}}{5.10^{10} M_{\odot}} \right)^{+0.07} \left(\frac{R}{R_{\text{MS}}} \right)^{+0.12}$
- ▶ $\mu_{\text{gas}} \propto (1+z)^{+2.60} \left(\frac{\text{SSFR}}{\text{SSFR}_{\text{MS}}} \right)^{+0.54} \left(\frac{M_{\text{star}}}{5.10^{10} M_{\odot}} \right)^{-0.33} \left(\frac{R}{R_{\text{MS}}} \right)^{+0.09}$

with:

- SSFR_{MS} from Speagle et al. (2014)
- R_{MS} from Van der Wel et al. (2014)

Can we explain these scaling relations with a simple theoretical models?

- ▶ The compaction scenario can provides a framework to understand evolution with Δ_{MS} : compaction above the MS triggered by efficient gaseous inflow, higher star formation efficiency; gas depletion below the MS, quenching
- ▶ μ_{gas} decreases with stellar mass due to feedback-induced winds
- ▶ Mass inflow rate from the cosmic web $\propto (1+z)^{2.5}$ (Dekel et al. 2013)
- ▶ However we would a priori expect $t_{\text{depl}} \propto t_{\text{dyn}} \propto t_{\text{Hubble}} \propto (1+z)^{-1.5}$, i.e. a sharper increase with time than observed: the difference might be explained by compaction events, through which the evolution of t_{dyn} is slowed down (Dekel et al. 2017, in prep.).

Interpretation in terms of compaction and replenishment

Episodes of gas compaction, depletion and replenishment could confine galaxies within the scatter of the Main Sequence until the final quenching occurs and explain the variations of t_{depl} and μ_{gas} with the offset from the MS

Tacchella et al. (2016)

The PHIBSS2 $z = 0.5 - 0.8$ sample

59 galaxies detected in CO(2-1) out of 61

- ▶ M_{star} from SED modeling
- ▶ SFR from UV+IR luminosities
- ▶ M_{gas} from CO(2-1) line luminosity
 - Molecular gas including Helium
 - MW-like α_{CO} conversion factor
 - Metallicity correction (cf. Bolatto et al. 13, Genzel et al. 12)
 - $r_{21} = L_{\text{CO}(2-1)}/L_{\text{CO}(1-0)} = 0.77$

Morphology: Bulge-disk decompositions with galfit from HST I-band images (exponential disk + $n = 4$ bulge) yield the disk radius R_d and the bulge-to-total luminosity ratio B/T

- 46 disk-dominated (84%)
- 9 bulge-dominated (16%)
- 36 with clear spiral or ring features (65%)
- 14 harbor bars despite the intermediate redshift (23%)

Freundlich et al. 2017, in prep.

The PHIBSS2 $z = 0.5 - 0.8$ sample

Freundlich et al. 2017, in prep.

The PHIBSS2 $z = 0.5 - 0.8$ sample

Freundlich et al. 2017, in prep.

Gas fraction and depletion time

- ▶ Intermediate values of the depletion time and the gas fraction between those at $z = 0$ (COLD GASS, Saintonge et al. 2011) and at $z = 1 - 2$ (PHIBSS, Tacconi et al. 2013).
- ▶ Mass-weighted averages:
 - $\langle \mu_{\text{gas}} \rangle = \langle M_{\text{gas}}/M_{\text{star}} \rangle = 0.53$
 - $\langle f_{\text{gas}} \rangle = \langle M_{\text{gas}}/(M_{\text{gas}} + M_{\text{star}}) \rangle = 0.31$
 - $\langle t_{\text{depl}} \rangle = \langle M_{\text{gas}}/\text{SFR} \rangle = 0.96 \text{ Gyr}$

Freundlich et al. 2017, in prep.

Contribution to the scaling relations

$$\log(y) = A + B \times \log(1+z) + C \times \Delta_{MS} + D \times \Delta_M + E \times \Delta_R$$

A, B from Tacconi et al. (2017)

---- PHIBSS2 $z=0.5-0.8$

— Tacconi et al. (2017)

Freundlich et al. 2017, in prep.

Galaxy-averaged Kennicutt-Schmidt relation

- ▶ The **striking linearity** argues in favor of similar star formation processes across cosmic time, although with a slow decrease of the depletion time.
- ▶ Taking the **disk size** R_d instead of the global half light radius reduces the scatter from 0.27 dex to 0.19 dex.

Freundlich et al. 2017, in prep.

The role of bulges

- ▶ While B/T increases, the overall SSFR and the gas fraction decrease as M_{star} increases.
- ▶ M_{gas} remains constant: assuming an evolutionary sequence of increasing B/T, this suggests an **ongoing supply of molecular gas** (accretion, HI to H₂ transformation)
- ▶ $M_{\text{star,disk}} = (1 - B/T) \times M_{\text{star}}$ decreases with B/T, which could suggest **stellar migration towards the bulge** (clump migration, bars, mergers).
- ▶ t_{depl} does not vary with B/T: **no trace of morphological quenching** so far. But our sample focuses on MS galaxies: little leverage, MS bulges potentially atypical or recent, in which case morphological quenching may not have settled down yet...

Freundlich et al. 2017, in prep.

Conclusion & perspectives

PHIBSS (Tacconi et al. 2010, 2013, Freundlich et al. 2013, Genzel et al. 2013):

- High molecular gas fractions at high z , turbulent disks
- Cosmic star formation history mainly determined by the molecular gas reservoirs
- Near linear Kennicutt-Schmidt relation, including at sub-galactic scales: similar star formation processes at different redshifts

PHIBSS2 (Genzel et al. 2015, Tacconi et al. 2017, Freundlich et al. 2017, in prep.):

- Scaling relations for the depletion time and the gas fraction as a function of redshift, stellar mass and offset from the main sequence
- At $z = 0.5 - 0.8$, intermediate values $\langle \mu_{\text{gas}} \rangle = 0.53$, $\langle f_{\text{gas}} \rangle = 0.31$ & $\langle t_{\text{depl}} \rangle = 0.96$ Gyr
- The KS relation is linear; using the disk size R_d instead of the global $R_{1/2}$ significantly reduces the scatter
- The dependences with B/T at $z = 0.5 - 0.8$ suggests an ongoing supply of molecular gas and may hint towards disk stars migrating to the bulge (clump migration, bars, mergers)

Perspectives:

- ▶ Better understand the scaling relations of t_{depl} and μ_{gas} from a theoretical point of view: bathtub model, compaction, comparison with hydrodynamical simulations.
- ▶ ALMA high resolution imaging and kinematics follow-ups (PI: J. Freundlich, ongoing): spatially-resolved KS relation, inner morphology of the disk, fate of the star-forming clumps